

Case Number: FORENSE TRIAL

Analysis performed by: SHDG

Date and time of analysis: 2025/12/12 11:31:32

Trace Analysed: Subungual swab 1

Analysis 1 of 1

Prosecution Hypothesis

Profile	Dropout Probability
POI	0.00
0 Unknown	

Defense Hypothesis

Profile	Dropout Probability
1 Unknown	0.00

Match Parameters

Probability of dropin: 0.0

Theta correction: 0.0

Allele Frequencies C:\Users\SHDG\Desktop\TRIALELICOS\FORENSE
TRIAL\Frequencies_STR000327_STRidER.csv

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Results

Locus	Pr(E Hp)	Pr(E Hd)	LR
D3S1358	1,00000E000	6,39102E-002	1,56470E001
D1S1656	1,00000E000	5,46208E-002	1,83080E001
D2S441	1,00000E000	1,53873E-001	6,49886E000
D10S1248	1,00000E000	1,27261E-001	7,85788E000
D13S317	1,00000E000	1,09152E-001	9,16153E000
PENTA E	1,00000E000	3,54008E-002	2,82480E001
D16S539	1,00000E000	3,47124E-002	2,88082E001
D2S1338	1,00000E000	4,37060E-002	2,28802E001
CSF1PO	1,00000E000	2,04551E-001	4,88876E000
TH01	1,00000E000	8,00029E-002	1,24995E001
VWA	1,00000E000	9,61250E-002	1,04031E001
D21S11	1,00000E000	2,04303E-002	4,89469E001
D7S820	1,00000E000	1,09897E-001	9,09943E000
D5S818	1,00000E000	6,73865E-003	1,48398E002
TPOX	1,00000E000	9,53897E-003	1,04833E002
D8S1179	1,00000E000	4,55269E-002	2,19650E001
D12S391	1,00000E000	1,34179E-002	7,45272E001
D19S433	1,00000E000	7,64215E-002	1,30853E001
SE33	1,00000E000	8,34634E-004	1,19813E003
D22S1045	1,00000E000	1,20582E-001	8,29314E000
FGA	1,00000E000	4,48335E-002	2,23047E001
Overall Likelihood Ratio			5,21816E028

Rare Alleles

All observed alleles are present in the population statistics.

Disabled Loci

The following loci were disabled for this analysis:

Locus	Reason
AMEL	Not present in the population statistics
DYS391	Not present in the population statistics

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Replicates

The following replicates were loaded for this analysis:

Filename	Replicate
C:\Users\SHDG\Desktop\TRIALELICOS\FORENSE TRIAL\SUBUNGUAL SWAB1.txt	Subungual swab 1

The contents of the profiles is listed below:

	Subungual swab 1
D3S1358	16 18
D1S1656	16 17.3
D2S441	10 14
D10S1248	14
D13S317	11 12
PENTA E	12 13
D16S539	9 10
D2S1338	19 20
CSF1PO	11 12
TH01	6
VWA	16
D21S11	32.2
D7S820	11 12
D5S818	7 10
TPOX	10 12
D8S1179	11 13
D12S391	15 20
D19S433	13 15
SE33	24.2 31.2
D22S1045	16
FGA	24 25

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Reference Profiles

The following reference profiles were loaded for this analysis:

Filename	Reference Profile
C:\Users\SHDG\Desktop\TRIALELICOS\FORENSE TRIAL\POI.txt	POI

The contents of the reference profiles is listed below:

	POI
D3S1358	16 18
D1S1656	16 17.3
D2S441	10 14
D10S1248	14 14
D13S317	11 12
PENTA E	12 13
D16S539	9 10
D2S1338	19 20
CSF1PO	11 12
TH01	6 6
VWA	16 16
D21S11	32.2 32.2
D7S820	11 12
D5S818	7 10
TPOX	10 12
D8S1179	11 13
D12S391	15 20
D19S433	13 15
SE33	24.2 31.2
D22S1045	16 16
FGA	24 25

Notes:

POI loci converted to homozygotic: [D10S1248, TH01, VWA, D21S11, D22S1045]

More Information

For more information about the probabilistic model implemented in LRmix Studio see:

- P. Gill & H. Haned. A new methodological framework to interpret complex DNA profiles using likelihood ratios. *Forensic Sci. Int. Genet.* (2013).
- H. Haned, et al., Exploratory data analysis for the interpretation of low template DNA mixtures, *Forensic Sci. Int. Genet.* (2012).
- P. Gill et al, DNA commission of the International Society of Forensic Genetics: Recommendations on the evaluation of STR-typing results that may include drop-out and/or drop-in using probabilistic methods, *Forensic Sci. Int. Genetics* (2012).
- Haned, H. & Gill, P. Analysis of complex DNA mixtures using the Forensim package, *Forensic Sci. Int. Genetics. Supplement Series* (2011).
- P. Gill, A. Kirkham and J. Curran, LoComatioN: a software tool for the analysis of low copy number DNA-profiles, *Forensic Sci. Int.*, (2007).
- J.M. Curran, P. Gill and M.R. Bill, Interpretation of repeat measurement DNA evidence allowing for multiple contributors and population substructure, *Forensic Sci. Int.*, (2005).
- Buckleton, J.; Triggs, C. M. & Walsh, S. J. *Forensic DNA evidence interpretation*, Chapter 4: 'Relatedness', CRC PRESS, 2005